

8T – Manifold Volcanos and Curvature Eruptions

O Manor

July 19, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of the 8T, of coupling constants under the first representation of net curvature, and varying to include many particle propagations – it is possible to reason lasers. It is also possible to make an analogy from geo-physics – electrons summations are dormant volcanos – and photons are the "magma eruptions" of net curvature on the matrix tensor.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Imagine that instead of having just one electron in the primordial, we will have an entire surface full of electrons. Each of them is emitting a net curvature of prime magnitude, and they all emit that magnitude at the same temporal segment on the surface of the matric tensor M.

$$\left[(24 * 5) + \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i) \right] + \gamma_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\odot : \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i) \rightarrow \gamma_i$$

The result of this construction is an immense eruption of net curvature off the manifold, similar to a volcano eruption in geo-physics, its concentrated amount of net curvature eruptions due to a positive summation of electrons that emit together, \odot as a time operator of all elements in the matric tensor. The eruption could be linearly polarized. In physics it is also known as "lasers".

The volcano is the summation of electrons, and the magma is the timed eruptions of photons. It is the same main equation just a different variation – applicable to many particles propagation. The energy of the eruption ray is proportion to the electron summation on the surface, which emit together and to inversely proportional to the area scattered by the eruption ray.

The volcano is the electrons on the surface and the magma is the photons, in their concentrated from can melt and cut steal. An analogy makes it easier to describe. So overall the "geo-surface" of the matric tensor is flat, due to the net curvature being relativity small portions and due to the fact arbitrary amount of curvature vanish into matter. The "geo-surfaces" or matric tensors in the 8T have dormant volcanos, which could suddenly become active, causing curvature eruptions of immense magnitude at a timed moment, analogous to magma eruptions.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)